

Appendix for - M2AR: A Web-based Modeling Environment for the Augmented Reality Workflow Modeling Language

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Appendix

This appendix includes additional tables and screenshots that illustrate the introduced M2AR modeling environment.

3D Notation. Table 1 shows the 3D notation of the *ARWFL* language concepts. For each *SceneType*, the visual notation is shown in the *3D Notation* column. If there is a dynamic visualization depending on attribute values, an example visualization is shown in the *Dynamic Example* column.

Color Brick Use Case. Figure 1 illustrates the *ObjectSpace* model, containing one *Detectable* marked as “origin” and three *Augmentations* visualized as green, blue, or red bricks. These augmentations are uploaded as GLTF files to the *Object 3D* attribute.

The right side of Figure 2 shows the *FlowScene* model for the color brick use case. It includes an *ObjectSpace* class instance referencing the *ObjectSpace* model, with an *Origin Port* for the AR environment. Additionally, the *FlowScene* model defines four timer *Conditions* and three *Statechange* class instances referencing *Statechange* models.

Figures 3 and 4 show screenshots of the color brick use case using the new 3D view of the Modeling Client.

Furniture Assembly Use Case. This use case guides the user through the assembly of a bedside table in AR.

Figure 5 shows the *ObjectSpace* model with ten *Detectables* and six *Augmentations*. Each *Detectable* has a unique image, and one is marked as the origin, referenced by the *FlowScene*.

Figure 6 shows the *FlowScene* model in the *3D Modeling Client*, referencing the *ObjectSpace*. The *FlowScene* contains an *Origin Port* linked to a *Detectable* and defines a linear workflow with conditions triggering *Statechanges*.

For each *Statechange* in the *FlowScene*, a *Statechange* model is created. Figures 7 and 8 show two *Statechange* models: “Init Middle-Plate” and “Leg 1 Positioned,” referencing *Augmentations* from the *ObjectSpace*. Setting attributes like visibility and positioning defines how the AR app will visualize *Augmentations* when a *Statechange* is triggered.

Once models (*ObjectSpace*, *FlowScene*, and seven *Statechanges*) are created, they can be exported as a JSON file and imported to the AR Engine. Figure 9 shows screenshots of the running AR Engine on a Samsung Galaxy Tab S7, displaying various states of the AR application.

Figure 2: Screenshots of the *FlowScene* of the color brick use case in the *3D Modeling Client*.

Figure 3: Screenshots of the first *Statechange* of the color brick use case in the *3D Modeling Client* in the 3D view.

Figure 1: Screenshots of the *ObjectSpace* of the color brick use case in the *3D Modeling Client*.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the second *Statechanges* of the color brick use case in the *3D Modeling Client* in the 3D view.

Concept	3D Notation	Dynamic Example	Concept	3D Notation	Dynamic Example	Concept	3D Notation	Dynamic Example	Concept	3D Notation	Dynamic Example
ObjectSpace	Detectable			Condition			Origin		Has Condition		
	Augmentation			Resolve			Start		Triggers		
	Anchored			Observer			End		Has Observer		
	Child			Exit			Statechange		Ends		
	Reference			ObjectSpace			Starts				
FlowScene											

Table 1: 3D notation of the ARWFML.

Figure 5: Screenshots of the ObjectSpace of the IKEA use case in the 3D Modeling Client.

Figure 7: Screenshots of Statechange one of the IKEA use case in the 3D Modeling Client in the 3D view.

Figure 6: Screenshots of the FlowScene of the IKEA use case in the 3D Modeling Client.

Figure 8: Screenshots of the second Statechange of the IKEA use case in the 3D Modeling Client in the 3D view.

Figure 9: Screenshots of the IKEA use case in the AR Engine.